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A Comparison Across the Iron Curtain. Continuities and Discontinuities of Residential Care in the Two German States

Abstract: *This article analyses the history of residential care for babies and toddlers in the two German states between the 1950s and the 1980s. A comparative perspective is employed to delineate similarities and differences in their developmental trajectories. Initially, parallel trends could be observed: in the first period, infant homes for babies and toddlers exhibited significant growth in East and West Germany, and the scientific discourse manifested conformity in both. Substantial disparities emerged only in the 1960s. In capitalist West Germany, these institutions were rapidly dismantled due to alarming findings from scientific research. In contrast, within socialist East Germany, the infant homes for babies and toddlers gradually vanished from public discourse while simultaneously enduring as an institution for residential care until the collapse of the German Wall in 1989.*

Keywords: *Residential care; comparative history; East and West Germany; attachment theory.*

Orphanage Childhood in Comparison – Theoretical Perspectives

Historical research on residential care for children has traditionally focused on national perspectives. Since the turn of the millennium, studies have respectively examined Western capitalist or Eastern state-socialist countries. These investigations have comprehensively demonstrated how cruelly children and youth were treated in infant homes across various nations. This single-state focus made sense, as the systems of residential care adhered to country-specific logics. For instance, in Canada and Australia, members of indigenous minorities were separated from their families of origin and raised in so-called "residential schools" (Regan 2010; Beresford et al. 2012). In Catholic-rigid Ireland, residential care primarily targeted "fallen mothers" (i.e., unmarried women and their children) (Ferguson 2007) – an influential trend also in Bulgaria (Kassabova 2023). In socialist East Germany, adolescents came under the

scrutiny of the state authorities when they defied the rules of socialism (Laudien & Sachse 2012).

These differences are not questioned hereafter, but this contribution advocates complementing national perspectives with comparative approaches. As Haupt and Kocka (1996: 13) outlined, some functions served by comparisons in historical research can be distinguished:

- *Heuristic Function:* A comparison can identify questions and themes that would otherwise be challenging to recognize.
- *Descriptive Function:* Examining a single case, such as the history of an educational institution, can be enriched by a more detailed profile when compared to other institutions.
- *Analytical Function:* When different developments become apparent through comparison, questions arise about the conditions of origin, course, and manifestation of these differences. Although these questions may not be entirely answered through a comparative approach, they can be addressed to some extent.

Comparative methodologies are less well established in historical sciences compared to sociology, political science, or educational research. This could be attributed to historians' skepticism toward abstract explanatory models. Additionally, the methodological complexity of historical comparisons may contribute to their limited use. Comparative historical analysis is considered a challenging procedure because it requires determining whether the chosen units of comparison (e.g., nations, regions) are appropriate and whether the actual objects of comparison (e.g., infant homes) are suitable. "Comparison," as stated by Haupt and Kocka (1996: 23), "is the business of conceptually explicit, theoretically oriented, analytical historians with a certain distance from the historicist tradition – and thus far, the business of a minority."¹

This article contributes a comparative history of residential care, focusing on a subject bearing two characteristics. Firstly, the emphasis is on infant homes for children under three years of age – a topic that has been scarcely researched. Secondly, the chosen units for comparison are the two German states – the capitalist Federal Republic of Germany (FRG) and the socialist German Democratic Republic (GDR) – during the Cold War. The starting point for these considerations is that at the end of the Second World War, residential care for children in the two parts of Germany hardly differed. Both states emerged from the German Reich after the defeat of National Socialism in May 1945; it can be as-

¹ This and all further translations from German by the author.

sumed that their populations and institutional structures entered into the post-war period under similar economic, social, and psychological conditions (early work by Kleßmann 1993; recently updated with a gender focus by Hagemann et al. 2019). Therefore, Germany offers a unique case allowing for the separation of structural similarities from political and discursive differences.

The benefits of inner-German comparisons are debated among historians. Klessmann (1993) and Jarausch (2004) advocated for this method, arguing that the histories of the two states were marked by "entanglement" and "demarcation" in multiple ways. Both the FRG and the GDR, as actors in the competition between socialism and capitalism, consistently distinguished themselves from each other, highlighting the political, economic, and social shortcomings and mistakes of the other side. Simultaneously, both states were entangled through preceding economic, cultural, and social developments. This necessitates an analysis of both divisive and opposing elements, as well as a focus on persisting traditions and mutual connections (Klessmann 1993: 41).

Möller (2007) was skeptical about comparing the two German states, arguing that both were integrated into contrasting blocs. From that perspective, any blurring of this fundamental dichotomy is deemed a failure to recognize the differences between dictatorship (GDR) and democracy (FRG). However, even Möller conceded that comparisons could be useful for selected topics. For example, juxtaposing female employment in the two states could be reasonable (though female unemployment would not), and certain aspects of family or social policy might also be appropriate to take into account, Möller argued. A similar topic will be addressed here.

This history of infant homes for babies and toddlers in the two German states begins with a quantitative analysis – a method particularly suitable for comparative approaches (section 2 below). Next, East and West German research on infant homes in the 1950s and 1960s is presented (section 3). A brief description of children's living conditions in these homes follows, along with a depiction of the partially similar, partially different developments in both states (section 4). Finally, an analysis is conducted on the societal and political reactions to scientific studies in the FRG and the GDR (section 5). The conclusion (section 6) revisits the methodological benefits and limitations of the comparative approach.

How Many Babies and Toddlers Were in German Infant Homes?

The German infant and toddler homes took in children between the ages of zero and three years for permanent residence. The first homes were founded at the beginning of the 20th century. Unlike the older orphanages, these homes looked after children of unmarried, working or sick mothers (Schlossmann 1923). The development of infant and toddler homes in the Weimar Republic (1918 – 1933) and under National Socialism (1933 – 1945) has not yet been comprehensively investigated. State statistics indicate that in Germany before the Second World War, approximately 55,000 children lived in orphanages and 26,000 children lived in infant and toddler homes (Statistisches Reichsamt 1940).

After the War, there was no longer a distinction between orphanages and infant homes. All these facilities were now called "infant and toddler homes" in West Germany and "permanent homes for infants and toddlers" in East Germany. There is no official data for the first post-war years, but comprehensive statistics exist from 1950 onwards. One could assume that these facilities were primarily institutions of the immediate wartime and post-war era with its extremely challenging conditions for families. However, official data presents a different scenario for both West and East Germany (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Capacity of baby and toddler homes, FRG and GDR, 1950/51 – 1989/1990, absolute²

² Sources: Statistisches Bundesamt, Wirtschaft und Statistik (various years) / Staatliche Zentralverwaltung für Statistik (various years). Own presentation.

In both German states, there was an increase in the capacity of residential care for babies and toddlers until 1960, followed by a decline, faster in the West than in the East. When considering demographic development and assuming each place was occupied by two children per year (Hartung & Glatkowski 1965; Pechstein 1968), the picture changes somewhat (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Utilization rates of baby and toddler homes, FRG and GDR, 1950/51 to 1989/1990, as a percentage of all age-matched children, weighted (2 children per place and year)³

Now differences between West and East Germany become apparent. In the Federal Republic, utilization increased slightly in the 1950s, only to decline from 1960 onwards. At the peak in 1960, approximately 1.3 per cent of all children under three years in West Germany temporarily lived in an infant home, according to the conservative assumptions of the calculation. This corresponds to about one in seventy children. The disappearance of these institutions began in the early 1960s and continued in the 1970s. By 1980, these infant homes no longer played an important role in the West German welfare state.

³ Sources: Statistisches Bundesamt, Wirtschaft und Statistik (various years) Staatliche Zentralverwaltung für Statistik (various years). Own presentation and calculation.

In East Germany, utilization grew more strongly in the 1950s, reaching its maximum also in 1960. However, at that time, the value was 2.7 per cent of age-matched children. This means that an estimated one in forty children under three years in the GDR temporarily grew up in residential care. Strikingly, the rates in East Germany remained high until the mid-1970s, with only slight declines thereafter. Even at point of the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989, these institutions had not disappeared in the GDR. At that time, according to these estimates, approximately one in sixty children under three years still temporarily lived in such institutions.

Attempting to quantify how many children were temporarily or permanently placed in these homes between 1950 and 1990, based on the assumption of two children per place and year, results in an estimated number of 1.3 million affected individuals. Assuming three children per place and year, this would yield a sum of 1.9 million children (Berth 2023a).

However, some uncertainties cannot be eliminated. Some babies and toddlers were placed in infant homes multiple times, so the total numbers may be higher than the real figures. Also, the lengths of stay may be different to what is assumed, leading to an under- or overestimation of the total numbers. In the GDR, there may have been overlaps with weekly crèches where children stayed from Monday to Saturday (Liebsch 2023). With regards to infant homes in the FRG, an overutilization of places leading to crowded homes was reported in the 1950s (Mausshardt 1962), and conversely, an underutilization in the late 1960s with only partially occupied facilities was also reported (Fuhrmann 1970). All these factors can lead to differences between what the data shows and what the real situation was. Nevertheless, statistical analyses indicate that these homes were not extremely rare. Despite the decline they further shaped the childhood of a minority.

Contemporary Perspectives on "Hospitalism" in the 1950s

In 1952, a photo reportage from a newly built infant home was published in the *Süddeutsche Zeitung* newspaper. The images depict, among other scenes, a young woman standing on a balcony, holding a warmly dressed toddler in her arms (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Photo reportage from a Munich infant home⁴

The white cap identifies the woman as a professional caregiver, not a mother. In the snow-covered garden below, there is a car with two pairs of skis on the roof. The caption reflects a perspective on early childhood prevalent at the time:

"It is an issue that occurs in almost every family: to whom to entrust the toddler when you want to go on holiday or are sick? Often, parents hesitate to place their child in an infant home because the baby might lack personal care there. In most cases, they are surprised how well the child has fared in the infant home." (*Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 01.03.1952: 4)

This newspaper article asserts that the babies in this institution were doing exceptionally well because they had everything they needed for life: regular and high-quality nutrition, meticulous cleanliness of clothing and bedding, and trained caregivers. Similar contributions can be found in newspapers of the 1950s and 1960s, both in West German

⁴ Source: *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 01.03.1952. Munich City Archives, Collection Rudi Dix, Signature FS-NL-RD2430A33

and East German media. Infant homes were often described in terms that made one think of vacations. The *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* (01.04.1961: 55) even avoided the term "infant home" and titled its sweetly romanticized reportage "One lives healthy and vibrantly in the 'Baby Hotel.'"

At the same time, psychoanalysts in the Anglo-Saxon world developed a contrasting perspective. René A. Spitz, John Bowlby, and Anna Freud published influential essays and books after the Second World War, emphasizing the importance of sensitive caregivers for the well-being of children. Bowlby, for example, wrote in his volume published by the World Health Organization (WHO):

"Essential for mental health is that the infant and young child should experience a warm, intimate, and continuous relationship with his mother (or permanent mother-substitute)". (Bowlby 1951: 11)

In an institution like those described above, babies and toddlers would lack vital security, which only arises when the caregiver remains constant, argued Bowlby. In the USA, a psychoanalytically grounded parenting guide advocating for warm, benevolent, sensitive childcare was published in 1946: With an estimated circulation of 50 million copies, Benjamin Spock's "The Common Sense Book of Baby and Child Care" became the best-selling parenting guide worldwide.

Interestingly, this perspective quickly gained traction in the German academic world (Berth 2021; Berth 2023 a & b). Although the dissemination of scientific knowledge was slower than it is today, it took less than two years for Bowlby to be widely noticed by German experts. The first to do so in West Germany was Annemarie Dührssen (1916 – 1998), a physician and psychoanalyst from Berlin who founded the journal *Praxis der Kinderpsychologie und Kinderpsychiatrie*. In an early issue, Dührssen introduced Bowlby's book, summarizing its essential findings and considerations in a comprehensive text (Dührssen 1953). Over time, there was a seeping effect, especially in West German professional journals in the field of residential care: Almost all pedagogical authors gradually embraced Bowlby's and Spitz's arguments, and the term "hospitalism" entered the vocabulary of experts. In return, descriptions of idyllic life in residential care in professional journals became rare by the end of the 1950s.

Bowlby's work was also read in East Germany during this time, as an analysis of GDR professional publications from the 1950s shows. Although Stalinism tightly controlled research, and usually every scientific

paper had to primarily refer to Soviet, supposedly ground-breaking work, the influential pediatrician Eva Schmidt-Kolmer (1913 – 1991) introduced the term "hospitalism" into the academic debate in the GDR. At least in the initial years, she referred positively to Bowlby's monograph (Schmidt-Kolmer 1957) and thus presented similar arguments to colleagues in Czechoslovakia (Henschel 2023).

Noticeable are parallels in research designs: the empirical work of both the West German Dührssen and the East German Schmidt-Kolmer compared the upbringing of babies and toddlers in various institutions – infant homes, nurseries, and their families of origin. Both, probably without knowing each other, consistently identified the greatest risks for child development in residential care. By the late 1950s, not only the West German but also the East German professional community was informed of the infant home risks.

Living Conditions in Baby and Toddler Homes

While infant homes' staff often romanticized the living conditions of children, as demonstrated in a widely circulated film by Bowlby collaborator James Robertson (Robertson, 1952; for the significant impact of this film, see Winnicott, 1959), the situation was often alarming from an external perspective. Reliable descriptions came from trainees who went to the infant homes for education. New to the job, they were not yet accustomed to what older professionals often considered commonplace and immutable. In 1957, a contribution from horrified young (and anonymized) trainees appeared in the West German professionals' journal *Unsere Jugend*:

"The number of caregivers is by no means sufficient. One lives in constant haste just to get somewhat finished at all. There is no time to think about why this infant does not want to drink today or why he cries. From the outside, everything seems well-ordered, impeccably clean, and hygienic. The main thing is that the weight curve is increasing. Children who eat poorly are held with their noses closed, and food is simply stuffed into them. While some children, standing between the knees of the caregivers, are fed at a lightning pace, others are tied to potties. They sit there for a long time, the shy and quiet ones the longest, as you have to deal with the screamers first. In bed, the children are re-tied. They are forced to lie on their backs the whole night." (*Anonymous, 1957, p. 102f.*)

Similar conditions prevailed in East Germany. In 1963, two trainees reported to health authorities about the conditions in a home in Blankenburg (Federal Archives DQ 1 6369). Once again, a picture of institutionalized violence and continuous neglect became evident, later

also documented photographically by researchers (Fig. 4). Even the Attorney General of the GDR investigated several cases of death, neglect, and abuse in infant homes and crèches (Federal Archives DQ1 1994).

Fig. 4. Force-feeding and Fixations⁵

The institutionalized children often did not possess toys or clothing. At night, they were sometimes restrained with straps in bed (Liebsch 2023), and during the day, they were frequently bound to their potties for extended periods. The poorly trained personnel focused on hygiene and cleanliness; pedagogy played little to no role. The work overload of the staff could be observed in both parts of the country; simultaneously, outsiders reported a cruel atmosphere where the humiliation of small children was commonplace. Legal responsibility for the facilities did not play a major role: in the GDR the infant homes were almost exclusively state-owned, in the FRG they were typically run by private individuals or welfare associations. Legal forms had no impact on the neglect of the children.

Research in psychology at the time produced some dramatic findings. Infant home toddlers acquired speech with significant delays and lasting limitations. For example, two-thirds of 18-month-olds in Zurich homes failed to speak five words, and similar findings were noted for two- and three-year-old home children in Hamburg (Stier 1963; Meierhofer & Keller 1966). Studies reported significantly reduced and even declining intelligence quotients. In Dührssen's testing (1958), a quarter of

⁵ *Source:* Meierhofer and Keller (1966: 120, 176). The publication by Swiss scientist Marie Meierhofer was to Switzerland what Annemarie Dührssen's works were to West Germany and Eva Schmidt-Kolmer's to East Germany: pioneering research on infant homes. Meierhofer's work described caregiver routines and the psychological consequences of institutional care in precise terms.

the children had an IQ below 85; another 50 per cent scored between 85 and 100. Similar values were found by Weidemann (1959) and Meierhofer and Keller (1966). Children frequently exhibited neurotic symptoms, including bedwetting and stereotypical rocking movements. Cognitive and emotional difficulties increased with the length of institutional stays, and those children who had lived in institutions from birth were the most affected (Pechstein 1968).

GDR research was somewhat less comprehensive than West German research, but significant developmental deficits in infant home children were evident. At least in the 1950s, East German publications could be seen as offering critique of infant homes (e.g., Schmidt-Kolmer 1957; Kiehl & Petermann 1959; Korff 1959) – albeit less explicitly, as openly contesting the importance of female/maternal employment was not permitted in the GDR.

The social background of infant home babies and toddlers had only been partially analyzed. Contemporary GDR research often avoided this topic; West German works from the 1950s and 1960s (Dührssen 1958; Weidemann 1959; Stier 1963; Hartung & Glattkowski 1965) offer indications of highly problematic parental living conditions. About 60 to 80 per cent of children in infant homes were referred to as "illegitimate," the West German legal term until 1970. The mothers of these children rarely completed education and were often unemployed; about 20 to 30 per cent were listed in records as prostitutes. About a third of the mothers were described as homeless, and a similar number had serious illnesses. Nearly none of them could rely on support – e.g., from grandparents; many were socially highly isolated.

Social and Political Reactions in the 1960s

The question remains about the consequences of the attachment-theoretical knowledge imported from the Anglo-Saxon world. In West Germany, the municipal youth welfare offices were particularly relevant because they decided whether the state paid for institutional care or even went to court to achieve the placement of a child in residential care.

Numerous initiatives indicate that the new perspective, inspired by psychoanalysts like Bowlby, was translated into practical policies in the West. The Stuttgart authorities, for instance, constructed new residential homes for unmarried mothers and their children in the early 1960s to prevent separate child placement (Scholl 1960). In the city of Mannheim, counselling centres developed a guide warning against the institutionalization of young children (Hiemenz et al. 1964). In Braunschweig and

Salzgitter, youth welfare offices aimed to prevent "the degrading, though hygienically impeccable assembly line care of so many small, homeless children," as Andriessens (1966: 333) wrote. The influential lawyer Hermann Riedel (1963: 111) referenced Bowlby in his widely distributed commentary on youth welfare law, stating that the worst family is better than the best institution. With this, Bowlby had entered German legal interpretation.

The transformation of municipal social policy soon manifested in official data: nationally, statistics showed a rapid decrease in residential care after 1960 – this corresponds to the steep decline in West Germany in Figure 1. Towards the end of this process, in the late 1960s, a member of the Bundestag stated in parliament that politicians were “aware of the dangers of hospitalism, i.e., harm caused by institutional care,” which is why the number of institutional spaces had been successfully reduced (Schroeder, 1968, p. 7543).

In East Germany, for ideological reasons, it was not possible to apply scientifically derived knowledge in practice. Pediatricians who examined the negative consequences of early institutionalization in the 1950s knew they were walking on thin ice. High maternal employment was one of the central state goals, partly because there was a dramatic shortage of labor and partly because of the GDR's concept of gender equality. Criticism of placing young children in daycare centres or institutions was unwelcome (Rosenberg 2021).

Therefore, pediatrician Eva Schmidt-Kolmer sought ways to improve the institutions. Numerous articles and books containing reform proposals were published, including an initial guide for education in daycare centres and institutions in 1957. Schmidt-Kolmer consistently advocated for stronger "pedagogical work" in the institutions, for which she also developed learning materials and instructions for their usage. Abolishing infant homes was not something she could (or would) demand.

However, even this was too much for the GDR authorities. In 1962, Stalinist Minister of Justice Hilde Benjamin wrote a letter to the Minister of Health sharply criticizing Schmidt-Kolmer's research on homes and weekly nurseries:

"Her views are in stark contrast to the needs arising from women's employment, and in particular the needs of women in management positions [...]. A woman who holds a position of responsibility in the state or in the economy and fulfils her social duties corresponding to that position cannot keep her eyes on the clock from 4:00 p.m. or 5:30 p.m. in order not to be late to take her child out of the crèche." (quoted in Plüchhahn 2000: 63).

Benjamin urgently demanded "ideological clarification by the doctors regarding the importance of placing young children in weekly homes for securing the enforcement of women's equality." Even if one only barely knew the Minister of Justice, her call for "ideological clarification" could be frightening. Some years earlier she had signed death sentences against "enemies of the republic" and had socialist Ministers put in prison.

Therefore, Schmidt-Kolmer officially communicated in the 1960s that hospitalism in socialist institutions had been completely overcome thanks to better pedagogical work. However, she knew that this was not true: "The manifestations of the so-called 'psychological' hospitalism in long-term institutional stays of infants, small, and preschool children are still clearly discernible," Schmidt-Kolmer wrote in 1962 in an internal memo (Federal Archives DQ 1 2004). Yet, the research and publication ban on this topic prevented infant homes in the GDR from being actively dismantled.

Thematic and Methodological Conclusions

In West Germany and East Germany in the 1950s, parallel developments in baby and toddler homes could be observed, as the institutions in both states underwent quantitative expansion. If they were discussed in the broader public sphere, this happened often in a naive and benevolent manner. However, with the psychoanalytical works of Anglo-Saxon research, this changed. The articles and books by John Bowlby, René A. Spitz, and Anna Freud from the early 1950s were soon read in both states. Empirical works by German pediatricians and psychologists followed, comparing infants and toddlers in various upbringing settings. Thus it became clear that the infant home was the most problematic environment, with children exhibiting significant deficits in cognitive and social development.

In the 1960s, differences between the two states became apparent. In West Germany, there was a rapid reduction of baby and toddler homes, a development driven by a combination of professional discussions, media discourse, and the actions of youth welfare offices. In East Germany, these institutions were scarcely researched and largely forgotten in public. Only with reunification in 1990 was the West German youth welfare system transferred to the East, leading to the closure of GDR infant and toddler homes within a few months – a transformation which has yet to be examined.

In terms of methodological assessment, some benefits of historical comparisons can be identified:

- *Descriptive Function*: Particularly in quantitative analyses, similarities and differences over time were discernible: baby and toddler homes expanded in the FRG and GDR in the 1950s; in the 1960s, they were slowly reduced in the socialist part of Germany but saw a more rapid reduction in the capitalist part. In this sense, the description initially points to a parallel development, then to a markedly different development. However, the question remains open regarding the reasons behind the increase in capacity in the 1950s, which surprisingly occurred in both German states. It could be speculated that the socio-moral concepts, especially concerning unmarried mothers, were still very similar in both German states during that period. This would need further analysis to clarify.

- *Analytical Function*: Several other similarities and differences in the history of caring for children under three years of age in institutions could be highlighted. These include scientific developments in West and East Germany, which initially converged but began to differ after the construction of the inner-German wall. Resemblances between living conditions in institutions were also notable. Hence, the comparative approach demonstrates analytical benefit.

One can summarize that the historiography of institutional care gains precision and analytical sharpness through a comparative design. This might be an argument for extending this perspective to other states on both sides of the Iron Curtain. It is likely that there are important similarities and differences in the history of caring institutions after World War II to be found.

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